

USORONKUZỊ ASỤSỤ IGBO N’ULỌAKWUKWỌ PRAIMARỊNA SEKONDİRİ

NAIJIRIA: IHE A GA-EME WEE MEJUPUTAYA-NA KLAASI

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ỤMỊ EDEMEDE

Edemede a lebara anya n’usoronkuzi (curriculum) asụsụ Igbo n’ulọakwukwọ primarị na sekondirị nke Naijiria. O Kọwara ka usoronkuzi asụsụ Igbo, Hausa na Yoruba siri malite n’ulọakwukwọ primarị na sekondirị Naijiria bụ nke bụ otu n’ime mputara nzuko nke e mere n’afọ 1969 a kpọrọ “National Curriculum Conference” n’asụsụ bekee. Odee edemede a gara n’ihu deputa ma kọwakwaa usoro nkuzi (teaching methods) dị iche iche bụ nke ndi-nkuzi nankuziasụsụ Igbo ga-agbaso ka nkuzi ha wee gaa were ware ufodu n’ime ha bụ ndia: usoro ke ekere, usoro ke egwuregwu, usoro ke nkọrịko dzg. O deputa kwara otutu omumu asụsụ Igbo naenwen’ulọakwukwọ ndia nke ufodu n’ime ha bụ, enweghi otutu nsogbu ndi nkuzi, omume ndinne no nna, akparamagwa umuakwukwọ na onwe ha, omume ndi goomenti na nke ndi okammuta n’ala Igbo. O gakwara n’ihu wee deputa mgbochi nsogbu ndia. Na mmechi, edemede a na-akowa na o buru na ndinkuzi na-akuzi Igbo etinnye uchu n’usoro nkuzi ndi e deputara ma kowaa na-edemede a, ya na o buru na nsogbu ndi edeputara ebe a abia na mgbochi,usoronkuzi (curriculum) asụsụ Igbo ga-abia na mmezu na praimarị na sekondirị Naijiria.

OKWU NDI GBARA OKPURUKPU: *Asụsụ Igbo, Praimarị, Sekondirị, Usoronkuzi, Usoro nkuzi*

ABSTRACT

This paper looks into the Igbo Language curriculum for primary and secondary schools in Nigeria. It explains how the curriculum of the three major Nigerian languages; Hausa, Igbo and

Yoruba came to be as a result of the 1969 National Curriculum conference. The paper went further to look into the different methods of teaching Igbo in Primary and Secondary Schools which can help in the successful implementation of the curriculum. Most of the methods include: Direct translation, Audio-lingual, playway and code-switching. The problems which Igbo Language teachers encountered were also looked into, thus; Attitude of the parents, shortage of Igbo teachers, lack of instructional materials, no funding from the government and the attitude of the elites. The paper also proffers some solutions to the enumerated problems. It concludes that if the above teaching, methods and the solutions to the problems are taken care of that the curricular of Igbo language in primary and secondary schools in Nigeria would be successfully implemented.

Keyword: Curriculum, Igbo Language, Primary, Secondary, Teaching Methods.

MMALITE

Iwu asụsụ bụ iwu jigidere ụzọ e si eji asụsụ arụ ọrụ n'obodo moọbụ n'ala ọbụla. mmalite iwu asụsụ dị otu a na Naijiria dika obodo nwere ọtụtụ asụsụ sitere n'aka atumaatu nke si n'aka PhelpsStoke n'afo 1922, bụ nke kwuru na a ga-eji asụsụ agburu ọbụla na-akaziri umuakwukwo nọ na laasi praimari nta. Nkwaputa ndi UNESCO n'afo 1953 nke kwuru na a ga-akuziri umuakwukwo ndi praimari iheomumu niile site n'asusu nne ha nyeere ntuziaka Phelps Stoke aka nke ukwu (Dom-Anyanwuand Iwuale, 2010:1). Kaosinadi, agburu di iche iche na Naijiria nyere mkpebi ndia nghota diiche iche maka-etu o siri gbagwoju ha anya. Ndi Hausa malitere iji asusu ha na mbaghara 'ugwu', ndi Igbo mitere iji asusu Igbo na mpaghara 'Owuna anyanwu' ebe ndi Yoruba malitereiji asusu Yoruba na mpaghara "odida anyanwu". Nke a mere o jiri di nmukwu mkpa na a gaenweiwu jikotara asusu Naijiria niile bu nke ndi bekee kporo (indigenous language policy).

Nkekachasi mkpa irutu aka bu na agwa agburu ndi a (Hausa, Igbo na Yoruba) kpasoro ntuzi aka

asusu nke Phelps Stokes abughi nke ga-eweta udo na idinotu n'etiti ha kama obu nke ga-ebute

ntisa n'etiti ndi Naijiria.

N'afọ 1969 e nwere nzukọ ntule uche n'ala Naijiria bu nke ndi otu Nigerian Educational Research Council (NERC) nke a na-akpozi Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) ugbua hiwere ma kwadokwa n'uzo obula, bukwa nke ndi niile omumu naanukun'obi ma ndi mmeputa omumu biara. Ebe a ka ha noro kwuo ma kpebie ihe ndi ga-abaraobodo anyi na umuakwukwo uru n'ogo mmuta obula, etu a ga-esi gboo mkpa ndi e nwere nammuta wee nwee ike weputa korikulum nke ga-abara obodo Naijiria na umuakwukwo n'onweha uru. Ogbako ntule-uche a bu iji mee ka omumu agumakwukwo wee baara ndi na-amu ya naobodo ha uru. Bukwa nke ga-enye aka na-ichekwa omenala na asusu anyi bu Naijiria (FRN,2013).

Mkpebi niile e mere na nzuko ntuleuche a putara ihe n'akwukwo ukwu a kporo *National Policy*

on Education, nke bu nke e biputara n'afọ 1977, ma degheria ya n'afọ 1981, 1998, 2004, 2008,

na 2013. Nke a bu akwukwo oru nke izizi ndi goomenti weputara banyere agumakwukwo n'ala

Naijiria. Otu ihe putara ihe na akwukwo oru a bu atuziaka maka omumu asusu na omenala Naijiria. Akwukwo a kpebiri:

(1) O siri na nkuzi niile a na-eme na praimari nta ga-abu site n'usoro asusu ara nne maobu asu agburu nwataakwukwo. Nke a ga-eme ka udo na idi n'otu di n'etili ndi Naijiria.

(2) Iji mee ka mmekorita, nkwekorita na iji kwado omenala Naijiria di iche iche, ha kpebiri na a ga-akuzi asusu Hausa, Igbo na Yoruba n'ulokwukwo sekondari dika asusu nke mbu na asusu nke abuo (NL1 & NL2). Ha siri na nwato obuta ga-amu asusu agburu ya dika asusu nke Naijiria nke mbu (NL1) ma mukwa otu n'ime asusu abuo ndi ozo dika asusu Naijiria nke abuo (NL2) ma oburu na enwere ndi nkuzi ga aguzi ha. (FRN,2013)

Ka e weputachara akwukwo oru nke agumakwukwo n'ala Naijiria, nkuzi omumu asusu Igbo dika asusu Naijiria nke abuo malitere n'afọ agumakwukwo 1982/1983. Obu Ntuaziaka a mere

omumu asusu Igbo jiri puta ihe na kurikulum ndi praimari na ndi sekondri Naijiria. Dika asusu

nke mbụ (NL1) na asụsụ nke abụọ (NL2) (Dom-Anyanwu, 2016).

Obanya (1985), kwenyere na mbunuche ọmụmụ ọbụla na-aba uru ma a mara sugharia ya nke oma na klaasi mgbe a na-akuzi ya. Ihe nke a pụtara bụ na nkuzi na ọmụmụ asụsụ na omenala Igbo agaghị ndị ire ma ọburu na ndị nkuzi na-akuzi ya agbasoghị usoro dị mma. Maka na nmejuputa kurikulum ọbụla dị n'aka ndị nkuzi bụ ndi na-eme ka mpụtara kurikulum ọbụla pata

ihe ma nwee nghota. Dom-Anyanwu (2016) siri na “ndi-ikuzi bụ ndi chi Igodo nkuzi na ọmụmụ ọbụla n'ụlọakwụkwọ; ewepu he, nkuzi na ọmụmụ agaghị enwe isi”. O gakwaran'ihu si na usoro nkuzi bụ ụzọ niileonyenkuzi na-agbaso wee akuzi nkuzi ya na klaasi, bụ ndi na-eme ka mmụta di mfe. Onyenkuzina-me ihe di iche iche ka nkuzi ga were were, kammuta wee dimfe, dika, ikwuokwu, iku aka, igba egwu, iju ihe ogugu, imeputa ihe na nkwago du nke umuakwukwo ga-esonye na ya ijingwa nkuzi di iche iche wee kuziere umuakwukwo dzg. Ihe ndi a bu usoro nkuzi ya. Ihe nke aputara bu na usoro nkuzi bu uzọ di iche iche onyenkuzi ọbụla na-agbaso bu nke ga-eme ka omejuputa mbunuche nkuzi ya ma mekwaa ka umuakwukwo muta ihe o na-akuziri ha. Usoronkuuzi bu otu n'ime ihe na-eme ka nkuzi na ọmụmụ asụsụ na omenala Igbo n'ụlọakwụkwọ primary na sekondiri di mfe n'ala Naijiria. Enweghi asusụ ọbụla a ga-akuzi nke oma na agbasoghị usoro nkuzi di mma.

Asusụ Igbo dikasusụ Naijiria

Asusụ Igbo bu otu n'ime asusụ ato a maaraama nwere ugwu n'ala Naijiria. Ndi na-asu ya kariri

nde mmadu iri abuo. Otut n'ime ha si Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, na Imo simpagbara Steeti

Delta, mpagbara Steeti Cross River nampagbara Steeti Rivers. Asusụ Igbo no n'alaka “New Benue Congo (NBC) Ke agburu asusụ Niger Congo. (Niger Congo Language family).

Obu na sanchori iri na itolu (19th century) ka e deturu asusụ Igbo nke izizi site n'aka ndi ozi uka

(missionaries). O bu eziokwu na asusụ Igbo siri n'aka ndi ocha ndi mgbaso ozi uka wee hu uzọ

ma nsogbu asusụ Igbo nwere rue taa bukwa n'aka ndi ocha ahụ ka ha siri bia site n'uzo aghugho

nke ha siri tughata ndi Igbo ufodu (Ikekeonwu, 2005).

Ha nwere otografii abuo nke ochie na nke lepus bu ndi ha jiri ruo oru ntoghata na mgbasa ozi

ha, bukwa ndi ha jiri dee akwukwo nsọ (Bible). Mana ndorondoro otografii ndia biara n'isi njedebe mgbe ndi otu ikwalite asusu na Omenala Igbo bidoro bu nke Maazi Chidozie Fedrick Ogbalu bu onye larala mmuo hiwere n'afọ 1949. SPILC na aha ichafu bekee nwere mbunuche di

iche iche:

- (a) Ikwubi ndorondoro otografii
- (b) ikwalite omumu asusu na omenala Igbo n'uloakwukwo.
- (ch) Ime ka asusu Igbo buru asusu mmekorita.
- (d) Ibipta akwukwo Igbo ma chikota agumagu onu ndi Igbo.
- (e) Iwechighata usoro obibi ndu ndi Igbo.
- (f) Ihoputa ndi ga-edeputa dishonari Igbo.
- (g) Ikwalite mmemme ndi Igbo di iche iche.

Obu ndi otu SPILC hiwere komitii a kporo Onwu komitii maka na aha onyeisi komitii ahụ bu Maazi S.E. Onwu. Ndi komitii a wepuru otografii abuo ndi ahụ wee weputazie nke ohuru bu nke

gbadoro ukwu na otografii ndi ochie. Ndi otu SPILC wee hazie ha nke oma wee kpoọ ya onwu

otografii bu nke e ji ede asusu Igbo taa dika asusu izugbe. Obu otografii Onwu wetarandorondoro otografii n'ala Igbo n'isi nkwusi. O bu kwa ya ka a na-eji ede akwukwo Igbo niile na

ihe obula gbasara asusu Igbo.

A na-amu asusu Igbo n'ulo akwukwo primary na sekondari Naijiria. dike asusu Naijiria nke mbu

na nke gbuo (NL1 & NL2).

MBUNUCHE EDEMEDE A (The Objectives of the Study)

Mbunuche edemede a gunyere ndia:

- Ka ndi nkuzi mata na praimary na sekondiri Naijiria nwere usoronkuzi (curricular) edeputara maka ikuzi Igbo. (To expose the Igbo language teachers on the primary and secondary curricular for Igbo language)
- Ka ndinkuzi mata usoro nkuzi di iche iche e ji akuzi asusu Igbo (Exposing teachers to

different methods of teaching Igbo).

□□Ka ha mata na-enweghi usoro nkuzi kacha ibe ya mma. (To let teacher know that there is no best teaching methods).

□□Ka ha mata na-enwere usoro nkuzi di iche na nkuzi Igbo di ka L1 na L2. (To let the teacher

know there are different methods in teaching IgboL1 and IgboL2)

□□I deputa nsogbu omumu asusu Igbo nwere na uzọ a ga-esi gbochie ha.(To x-ray the problems the Igbo language teachers encounter in teaching the language as well as the preferred solutions).

USORO NKUZI DI ICHE ICHE MAKA NDI PRAIMARI NA SEKONDIRI NAJIRIA (Teaching Methods)

Nke a bu usoro onyenkuzi na-agbaso wee kuziere umuaka no na praimari na sekondiri asusu Igbo ka ha wee ghotu ya nke oma. E wee usoro nkuzi di iche iche. Onyenkuzi asusu Igbo obula

kwesiri ima didi usoronkuzi di iche iche ma marakwa etu o ga-esi were ha aru oru. O na ewutu

m na ufodu ndinkuzi amaghi nke ha riri ma a bia n'ihe gbasara usoronkuzi na-etu e si eji ha aru

oru na klaasi naani ihe ndinkuzi di otu a maara bu nzuodee na ugboojii. Nke a na-egosi na ufodu

ha amughi asusu Igbo na ka esi akuzi ya n'uloakwukwo di elu di ka koleeji mmuta ukwu na mahadum. Otu ihe ndinkuzi asusu Igbo ga-amata banyere nkuzi asusu Igbo n'uloakwukwo aimari na sekondiri bu na enweghi usoronkuzi obula kachasi ibe ya mma. Usoronkuzi obula onyenkuzi jiri mee ka mmuta di mfa ma ga were were bu ezigbo usoronkuzi.

Onyenkuzi asusu Igbo ga na-enye umuakwukwo ya ohere ka ha na-asu asusu Igbo na klaasi. O

ga enye ha ohere ka ha na-ekwu okwu na klaasi. O ga-akpalite mmuo ha nkeoma ka ha ghara idamba. Ya na umuakwukwo ya ga na-emme mkparitauka n'okwu Igbo oge obula. O ga na-enweihu ochi mgbe niile ma na-enyekwa ha osisa n'ihomume o nyere ha-mee. O ga na-akuziri hasite n'a ihe ndi di mfe wee rue na ndi tara akpu site n'ihe ha mabu ama wee rue na

nke ha naamaghi, O ga-agbado ukwu n'okirikiri ebe ha no wee na-aju ha ajuju. O ga na-ajalite mmuo ha

ma ha zaa ajuju nke oma ma kwalitekwa mmuo ha mgbe ha na-azataghi ajuju nkeoma. Nke a ga

eme ka ha ghara ida mba n'omumu asusu Igbo.

Usoronkuzi asusu Igbo n'uloakwukwo praimari na sekondiri gunyere ndia:

Usoro ke ekere (Direct method): Nke a bu usoro onyenkuzi, na-agbaso wee na-akuzi Igbo naetinyeghi

asusu ozo. O bu iji asusu Igbo akuziri ndi na-amu asusu Igbo. Nke a na-adi ire ma onyenkuzi nwee ike na-etinye mmeghari ahụ di iche iche, ma nyekwa umukwukwo ohere ka ha

nwee mgbuta n'uzo nke aka ha na-abughi n'uzo mmanye. Onyenkuzi ga-agbaso usoro a site najingwankuzi di iche iche bu nke ga-enyere umakwukwo ahụ aka na mmuta ha.

Usoro ke Nkorinko (Discussion method): Usoronkuzi a na-eme ka ndinkuzi nye umakwukwo

ohere ka ha sonye na nkuzi na omumu na klaasi. Obanya (1985) siru na obughi naani na umakwukwo na-esonye na ihe a na-akuziri ha, na usoronkuzi a na-emekwa ka mmekorita na mkparitauka na-aga nke oma site n'aka onyenkuzi rue na nke umakwukwo.

Onyenkuzi ga na-agaghari no klaasi wee choputa na enwere nsogbu umakwukwo nwere bu nkeo ga-enye aka wee dzie. N'ikpeazu, onyenkuzi ga-agwa ha ebe ha na-emetaghi nke oma maduziakwa ha uzo na ha.

Usoro ke Egwuregwu (Play-way method): Usoro a na-eme ka umakwukwo sonye n'ihe a naakuziriha bukwa nke na-eme ka ha ghara igho aghughu. Nke a na-adi mma ikuzi asusu na agumagu Igbo. Usoro nkuzi a na-amasi umakwukwo nke ukwu n'ihina ha huru egwuregu n'anya.

Usoro ka nsughari Utosusu (Transilition method): Usoronkuzi a kachasi mma iji kuziere ndi

na-amu asusu Igbo dika asusu nke abụ (NL2). O na-akowa maka ihe ndi di mkpa n'asusu Igbo.

Nke a bu maka imu asusu obula dika asusu nke abuo bu ihe mmadu kpacha anya ya wee na amusite na-itinye uchu.

Usoro ke mmakorita Nkwukorita (Discussion method): Usoro a di nnukwu mkpa na-ikuzi

asụsụ Igbo dika asụsụ nke mbụ na asụsụ nke abụọ. Ọ na-eme ka ụmụakwụkwọ na-ekwukoritara

onwe ha okwu na klasị na n'ebe ọbụla ha hụrụ onwe ha. Nke a bụ maka na ọ bụ site na nkwukorita ụka ka asụsụ si eto, onyenkuzi ọbụla ga-agba mbọ iji usoro nkwukorita ụka wee naakuziri ụmụakwụkwọ ya na klasị n'ogo nkuzi ọbụla.

Usoro ke kodu Suwiichi (Code-Switching method): Usoro a bụ usoro onyenkuzi na-eji kuziere ụmụakwụkwọ ya mgbe ya bụ onye nkuzi na-ụmụakwụkwọ nwere ike ighota asụsụ abụọ

ha na-asụ na klasị. Onyenkuzi na ewebata asụsụ ọzọ bụ nke ụmụakwụkwọ ya ga-aghota na nkuzi ya iji wee kuziere ha ihe tara ha akpọ n'asụsụ nke ha na-amụ ma ọbụ iji wee kowaara ha ihe ha na-aghota nke oma na asụsụ ha na-amụ bụ nke ndị bekee na-akpọ (target language) n'asụsụ bekee. Mgbe onyenkuzi mechara nke a, ọ ga-echigha azụ n'asụsụ nke ọ jibu akuzi nkuzi ya.

Usoro ke Odio-lingual (Audiolingual method): Nke a na-agbado ụkwu na-nkuzi asụsụ Igbo site na mkparita ụka. Usoro a na-eme ka ụmụakwụkwọ kwu gharịa ma mugharia ihe ha na-anụ

ugboro ugboro bụ nke ga-enyere ha aka ighota ha nkeoma ma gharakwa ichefu ha ọsọsọ. Onyekwuzi asụsụ Igbo ọbụla ga-agba mbọ iji usoro a akuzi nkuzi ya ka ụmụakwụkwọ nwee ike sonye n'ihe ha na-amụ.

Usoro ke ogbe (Community method): Nke a bụ usoro na-eme ka ụmụakwụkwọ sonye na ihe onyenkuzi ha na-akuzi site n'ibute uzọ kwuo ihe ọ choro ime n'asụsụ omumụ. Nke a na-enyere mmụta aka nke nkwa okochasi na ndi na-amụ asụsụ Igbo dike asụsụ nke abụọ.

Usoro nkuzi ndi ọzọ gu nyere: Usoro njem nleta (Excursion method), usoro ke ajuju (question method) usoro ke ugwara (Eclectic method)

Usoro nkuzi niile ndia e deputara na kowasi ha ga-adị ire ma ọburu na onyenkuzi, ụmụakwụkwọ

na ihe omumụ nwee ike mekorita nke oma site na-iwebata ihe ndi ozo ahụ na-enyere onye nkuziaka na nkuzi ya. Dika, Omume ndi nne na nne, Omume ndi goomenti, aikparamegwa ndi isiuloakwuko, mmasi umakwukwo, Omume ndi okammuta (Elites), inwe ngwa nkazi di iche iche, ulo okpu na ulo omenala Igbo, mkpalite mmuo umakwukwo na ebe uloakwukwo no.

Nsogbu a na-enwe na-ikuzi asusu Igbo

Nkuzi asusu Igbo nwere nsogbu di iche iche na priamari na sekondiri Ha bu ndia:

- Enweghi ndinkuzi zuru oke
- Enweghi ndinkuzi a zuru nke oma n'asusu na omenala Igbo.
- Agaghi nzuko ntule iche (seminar & conference)
- Ejighi nkuzi na omumu asusu Igbo kporo ihe.
- Mmegide omumu asusu bekee na-megide omumu asusu Igbo
- Enweghi ngwankuzi zuru oke ma o bu ndi di iche iche.
- Iwepu onyenkuzi site na mbughari ndi oru (transfer)
- Mgbanwe ndi nkuzi
- Enweghi otutu akwukwo Igbo
- Agaghi njem nleta.
- Ndi nkuzi Igbo ufodu amaghi ndi iche di n'etiti IgboL1 na IgboL2
- Ufodu ndi nkuzi Igbo anubeghi Igbo korikulum mbu.
- Ufodu ndi nkuzi na-akuziri ndi L1 na L2 site n'igbaso otu usoronkuzi.
- Enweghi nkwado ndi nnee na nna, na ndi goomenti.

Mgbochi Nsogu:

- Ndi goomenti ga-achota ndi nkuzi di otutu na-nkuzi asusu na omenala Igbo.
 - A ga-ewebata ndi muru asusu Igbo n'uloakwukwo ukwu ka ha na-akuzi Igbo.
 - Onyenkuzi Igbo obula ga-enwe korikulum omumu asusu Igbo.
 - Ndi goomenti na ndi isiuloakwukwo ga-agba, mbo weta ngwa nkuzi e ji akuzi Igbo ebe o zuru ka.
 - Ndinkuzi Igbo ga na-aga nzuko ntule uche kwa oge kwa oge.
 - A ga-enwe nzuko nkowa nke IgboL1 na IgboL2 ka ndi nkuzi Igbo wee ghota ha nke oma.
 - Ndi nne na nna, na ndi okeo mmuta ga-agba mbo na-akwado omumu asusu Igbo.
- Okachasi n'ebe umu ha no. Nke a ga-eme ka umu aka ha nwee mmesi n'omumu ya bu

asụsụ, bụkwa nke ga-enyere ha aka imata agbụrụ ha si pụta ma matakwa omenala ndi be ha. Biko aka anyi gbakolatanu onu nyuo maamiri ka o wee gbaa ufufu. Asusụ anyi agaghi anwu. Igbo ga-adi.

MMECHI

Ọburu na ndinkuzi na-akuzi asusụ Igbo na praimari na sekondiri Naijiria etinye uchu n'usoro nkuzi ndi a edeputara ma kowa n'edemede a, ma werekwa ngwa nkuzi di iche iche kuziere umuakwukwo ha, omumu asusụ Igbo ga-aga were were na klaasi. Ozokwa, o buru na enwee ezigbo mgbochi na nsogbu ndi e deputara ma kowaakwa n'ederede a, usoronkuzi (curriculum) naomumu asusụ Igbo n'uloakwukwo praimari na sekondiri nke Naijiria ga-abia na mmezu. O

gaghi abuzi naani n'akuko na n'akwukwo ka a ga na-ahu ya.

Nkuzi na omumu asusụ Igbo aburego ihe kwu chim n'uloakwukwo priamari na sekondiri Naijiria. Dike otu n'ime asusụ ato ndi a mara amara na Naijiria, mbunuche nkuzi asusụ Igbo na

priamari na sekondiri agaghi abia na mmezu ma ọburu na-enweghi ndinkuzi rijuru afo na nkuzi

ya bu asusụ. Ikwu maka naani usoro nkuzi agaghi eduba na-imuta asusụ Igbo nke oma. E nwere

ihe ndi ozo di mkpa dika, omume ndi goomenti, ndi nne na nna, ndi okammuta, ngwa nkuzi na

ntinye uche ndinkuzi na umuakwukwo gakwa enyere usoro nkuzi onyenkuzi aka ka omumu na

nkuzi asusụ Igbo n'uloakwukwo priamari na sekondiri Naijiria gaa were wee ma tookwa ato mameekwa ka usoronkuzi (curriculum) priamari na sekondiri bia na mmejuputa.

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